

Sustainable Lending and Network Dynamics

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Introduction

The research investigates whether interconnectedness in the syndicated loan market differs between green and sustainability-linked loans compared to traditional loans and how it has evolved in the past few years. Interconnectedness, crucial for assessing the systemic importance of global banks, can amplify systemic risk through the spread of financial shocks and shared loan portfolios (FSB, 2010; Gai et al., 2011; Acemoglu et al., 2018; Cai et al., 2018). The growing focus on sustainable finance has led to examining the impact of ESG practices on interconnectedness among financial institutions (Houston et al., 2018), exploring how the adoption of sustainable lending influences the overall stability of the financial system.

Methods

The study applies a method to evaluate interconnectedness in the sustainable loan market by considering how much loan activity is shared between banks (De Novellis et al., 2024). This indicator reflects the extent to which banks participate together in green and sustainability-linked loans. Through an analysis, measures of interconnectedness are derived, focusing on individual banks and their loan-sharing levels. Additionally, the variation in these connections is considered. A further analysis groups banks into categories based on their network traits, offering insight into the structure of interbank connections in this market.

Results

The analysis is expected to reveal that banks exhibit higher interconnectedness in sustainable loans compared to non-sustainable ones, with some banks showing stronger ties. Sustainable interconnectedness is anticipated to have increased in recent years for newer lenders, while possibly decreasing for those active in earlier years. The study is likely to

identify distinct community structures within the sustainable loan market, suggesting potential clustering around specific practices. Cluster analysis is expected to highlight different risk profiles based on interconnectedness and concentration of loan sharing. This approach aims to offer insights for understanding bank networks and monitoring systemic risk in the context of sustainable finance.

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